

NUMERICALLY PREDICTING THE MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF A LARGE SMART COMPOSITE STRUCTURE UNDER STATIC LOADS

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ABSTRACT

The DECID2 French National Project (FUI, DGCIS) of a platform of large dimensions made entirely of smart composite materials was carried out within the period 2008 - 2012. Two demonstrators were manufactured and installed, the target being to experiment and model their performances under mechanical and environmental aging. Despite significant advances, a number of issues have not been solved yet within the framework of this project and are related to the negative effects of bolt fastening on the profiles of composites. In this study, numerical simulations were run to determine the mechanical behavior of a bolt-fastened platform composed primarily of unidirectional E-glass composite beams and polypropylene honeycomb sandwich slabs under static three-point bending loads. A finite-element model of the on-site structure was employed using Abaqus FEA software. Results yielded thresholds for matrix tensional and compressional damage initiation which will be used in future non-destructive tests on the structure.

1 INTRODUCTION

The favorable mechanical properties of polymer matrix composites, their excellent corrosion resistance, strength-to-weight ratio, and ease of installation have brought about their increased use in structures in various industrial fields. Nevertheless, their sustainability and mechanical performance over the long term remain issues that need to be addressed. Therefore, it is necessary to develop suitable and reliable structural health monitoring techniques that will enable comprehensive and precise estimates of strain in various localizations and smart composites meet this demand.

Such was the overall aim of the DECID2 project, the construction of a pedestrian platform made solely of E-glass-epoxy pultruded composite, and with minutely sized optical fiber sensors embedded longitudinally along the fiber alignment direction (see Figure 1). The sole means of part attachment used was single- and double-lap bolted joints. To minimize delamination onset during the drilling of bolt holes, the use of larger beam cross-sectional thicknesses has been shown to be effective [1]. A host of studies have been carried out on the behavior of bolted joints in composites [2, 3, 4, 5, 6]. Some, including that of Liu et al. [7] have shown that high speed drilling and low feed rates may mitigate the delamination-inducing effects of fastener hole drilling, and in the long run, delay the onset of delamination in the lifetime of a composite joint. Nevertheless, the DECID2 project having commenced prior to the publishing of these studies, conventional drilling methods were utilized.

The optical sensors or Fiber-Bragg-Gratings (FBGs), which are currently the subject of intense research, provide on-demand information on the mechanical behavior and health of these materials during the course of an experiment. The advantages of this method of non-destructive testing (NDT) abound. However, a number of drawbacks exist, two of which are: the inability to test the composites

to failure without inflicting permanent damage on the structure, and the need to analyze the mechanical impact of the presence these "deformities" in the laminae. Several possible sensors for sensor embedding in the large-scale smart composite structure, DECID2, have been previously studied in detail [8, 9]. Extensive work has also been devoted to the study of the effects of UV-radiation on the mechanical performance of DECID2 platform [10].

The driving goal of this segment of the DECID2 project[11] was to numerically predict the mechanical behavior of the aforementioned platform under static loads from the elastic region right up to the onset of damage. By so doing, the behavior of composites at damage initiation could be predicted, and a safe maximum stress value fixed as a threshold in future NDT experiments on the structure. The areas around bolt-holes were investigated in more detail, due to the higher stress distribution and likelihood of damage initiation in those regions. A number of studies have highlighted the impact of bolt torque and bolt hole clearance [12, 13] on delamination damage of composites, with the former delaying joint stiffness loss and increasing 2% offset bearing strength, and the latter doing the very opposite. However, in light of the enormity of computing time required for including these phenomena in the numerical model of the whole structure, they were not covered in this study.

Figure 1: The DECID2 platform from different viewpoints. The platform consisted of E-glass--Epoxy I-beams and honeycomb sandwich slabs assembled with bolts and nuts as sole fasteners in single and double lap joints. The railing depicted was not included in the analysis.

2 MODEL AND SIMULATION

2.1 CAE Model

The DECID2 platform was modeled as a 3D shell using Abaqus CAE/Standard finite element analysis software (see Figure 2a). Materials present included E-glass-Epoxy composites for the beams, and a composite-honeycomb sandwich for the slabs. Following the prototype's design as closely as possible, all parts were assembled with single or double lap joints, with bolts of diameter 10mm for fasteners. The fasteners, which in the physical prototype were steel bolts and nuts, were modeled as connector elements of bushing type CONN3D2 with all modes of deformation unconstrained (see Figure 2b). This served to reduce simulation time considerably as the total number of bolts in the structure was above three hundred.

Composite parts were modeled using the *composite layup* sub-module, as conventional shell laminae of ten unidirectional plies, each of thickness 1.2mm, zero rotation, and three integration points. The layup coordinate system was given a *discrete* definition and the shell reference was measured from the middle surface in all cases. On the other hand, the honeycomb parts were modeled using the *section* sub-module as homogeneous continuum shells with specified thickness using the Simpson integration rule and five integration points. The mechanical properties of these materials may be found in Table 1.

Figure 2: (a) CAD model of composite platform created with Abaqus CAE/Standard to the geometric and material specifications of the physical prototype. (b) Bushing connector locations in the model. These were used as fasteners, in place of actual steel bolts, to optimize computing time.

		E-glass Composite	Honeycomb
Density	[kg/m ³]	2100	65
E_1	[MPa]	39000	30
E_2	[MPa]	8600	30
ν_{12}		0.28	0.3
G_{12}	[MPa]	2500	5
G_{13}	[MPa]	2500	5
G_{23}	[MPa]	8500	5

Table 1: Mechanical properties of materials studied.

2.1 Simulation

The simulation was effected in two steps: *Initial* and *Load Applied*. As the names imply, boundary conditions were initiated in the first step, and loads were applied in the second step (and its sub-steps) for a stipulated amount of time. To recreate the actual situation of the physical platform prototype, a static three-point bending 3D scenario was executed in the Abaqus environment, with line loads applied along the platform center, midway between supports, and all four supports modeled as encastre surfaces (see Figure 3). Loads included the aforementioned central line force and the negligible but nonetheless present effect of gravity.

Figure 3: CAE model showing: (a) Points of application of the load and boundary conditions. A line force was applied at platform center, and all four supports modeled as fixed surfaces (encastre). (b) Mesh pattern around fastener holes. Quadrilateral conventional shell elements were used for all parts.

Composite and honeycomb parts alike were modeled and meshed as conventional shell 4-node elements *S4R*, with reduced integration, hourglass control, and finite membrane strains. The *Free* meshing technique was utilized in creating the mesh using a medial axis algorithm.

In order to facilitate the investigation of damage initiation and propagation in the structure, the use of a set of failure criteria was imperative. The Hashin criteria were selected for their ease of use within the Abaqus environment, and the possibility of examining fiber and matrix tensile and compressional damage separately [14].

Tensile Fiber failure $\sigma_{11} > 0$

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_T}\right)^2 + \frac{\sigma_{12}^2 + \sigma_{13}^2}{S_{12}^2} \geq 1 \quad (1)$$

Compressive Fiber failure $\sigma_{11} < 0$

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_C}\right)^2 \geq 1 \quad (2)$$

Tensile Matrix failure $\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33} > 0$

$$\frac{(\sigma_{12}^2 + \sigma_{13}^2)^2}{Y_T^2} + \frac{\sigma_{23}^2 - \sigma_{22}^2 \sigma_{23}^2}{S_{23}^2} + \frac{\sigma_{12}^2 + \sigma_{13}^2}{S_{12}^2} \geq 1 \quad (3)$$

Compressive Matrix failure $\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33} < 0$

$$\left[\left(\frac{Y_C}{2S_{23}}\right)^2 - 1\right] \left(\frac{\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}}{Y_C}\right) + \frac{(\sigma_{22}^2 + \sigma_{33}^2)^2}{4S_{23}^2} + \frac{\sigma_{23}^2 - \sigma_{22}^2 \sigma_{23}^2}{S_{23}^2} + \frac{\sigma_{12}^2 + \sigma_{13}^2}{S_{12}^2} \geq 1 \quad (4)$$

Where X_T , X_C , Y_T and Y_C are the principal plane components of the tensile and compressive strengths of the laminae respectively. Likewise, S_{12} , S_{13} , and S_{23} are the allowable shear strengths in the principal directions, while σ_{ij} are the components of the stress tensor. For the purpose of these analyses, the criteria were simplified for a laminar plane stress situation.

Parameter [Unit]	Value
Longitudinal Tensile Strength [MPa]	766.5
Longitudinal Compressive Strength [MPa]	686.32
Transverse Tensile Strength [MPa]	538.65
Transverse Compressive Strength [MPa]	165
Longitudinal Shear Strength [MPa]	71
Transverse Shear Strength [MPa]	71
Cross-product Term Coefficient	-0.5
Stress Limit	0

Table 1: Parameters for Hashin damage analysis

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Stress propagation prior to damage

A series of simulations were run for static conditions on the platform under three-point bending loads. As expected in this kind of configuration, higher stress values were observed around the supports and center of the platform (see Figure 4a). The maximum stresses observed for any given load, however,

were located around the fastener holes. As such, these stresses were examined in more detail (Figure 4b).

Figure 4: Mises stress contour plot of platform. (a) Platform overview (b) Region around bolt holes. Regions around the supports and area of application of the line force showed high stress concentration, with fastener holes in these regions having the highest values.

Glass fiber reinforced plastic structures manufactured by pultrusion cost about the same per kilogram as their steel counterparts. Thus, the difference in overall manufacture and assembly costs between GFRPs and steel is usually dictated by the joining method utilized. In general, fastener methods are significantly less expensive than bonding or stitching methods. However, they are less efficient. Studies on the effect of bolt holes in composite joints (aforementioned) have shown that they lead to high stress concentration regions and accordingly, poorer mechanical performance compared to bonded joints. The Mises stresses experienced by the platform for a range of loads, as well as the obtained stress-strain curves, are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Stress plot for platform under static loads. (a) Stress/Load (b) Stress/Strain. Charts include zero-damage and damage initiation and propagation regions, but however do not include failure points.

It should be noted that, given the brittle nature of E-glass composites, these linear curves represent the mechanical behavior of the platform right from the zero-damage stresses to stresses at which extensive matrix damage is initiated and propagated.

Figure 6: Hashin Criteria for damage initiation in platform. Damage was predicted in the matrix, first due to tension, then due to compression at values of 74MPa and 211.5MPa respectively

3.2 Fiber and matrix damage initiation

To characterize the behavior of the material at the onset of damage, the Hashin criteria were utilized. Four damage initiation criteria—matrix tension, matrix compression, fiber tension, and fiber compression—were computed over a range of stresses and can be seen in Figure 6. As the names imply, these criteria predict damage in the matrix and fiber due to tensile and compressive stresses respectively with a value of 1 being the damage threshold. The criteria predict matrix damage due to tensile load first at a Mises stress value of 74MPa, and subsequently, damage due to compressive stress in the matrix at a Mises stress value of 211.5MPa. On the other hand, even at stresses higher than 400MPa, the fibers remain undamaged with Hashin values below 0.8.

The Mises stress contour plots of the platform at the point of matrix tensile damage are shown in Figure 7. An increase in stress concentrations around the fastener holes is clearly evident, and mode I tensile crack initiation shown to be highly probable.

Figure 7: Mises stress contour plot of platform just prior to damage. (a) Platform overview (b) Region around bolt holes. High stress concentration regions were located around the supports and area of application of the line force, with fastener holes in these regions having the highest values. Stress patterns at the holes show probable mode I tensile crack initiation.

Within the same laboratory in which the current project was carried out, parallel to the DECID2 project, several experiments were run on a scaled down version of an E-glass composite beam of rectangular cross-section. Subjected to a three-point bending scenario, static loads were applied to the specimen and with the aid of the acoustic emission technique, a stress threshold for damage initiation of 75MPa was obtained [15]. Thus, comparing previous experimental and current numerical results, a strong similarity is observed. The Hashin criteria model evidently predicts the damage initiation threshold with a reasonable margin of error, albeit conservatively.

The predicted stress thresholds will be used in subsequent non destructive tests on the physical prototype. However, the importance of fatigue analysis in examining and comprehensively predicting the mechanical behaviour of composites is immense. Therefore, a low-cycle numerical fatigue analysis of the DECID2 platform is already underway and results will be published in due course.

4 CONCLUSION

In this study, the overall mechanical behavior of an E-glass—epoxy composite platform subjected to static loads was investigated numerically at low stresses and around the damage initiation threshold. The platform was modeled as a conventional shell in 3D space, with geometric and material specifications matching those of the physical prototype. Simulations were run for a wide range of loads. Fastener holes were found to have the highest stress values, with results showing probable mode I tensile fracture initiation and propagation. The matrix was found to succumb to damage significantly earlier than the fibers, with damage initiation thresholds of 74MPa and 211.5MPa for matrix tension and compression respectively. These values corroborate experimental results obtained in previous segments of the project. Numerical analyses carried out on a sensor-embedded beam of the platform predicted minimal change in stiffness between both scenarios. Results from subsequent simulations with slightly larger optical fiber diameters also showed negligible change in beam stiffness and stress limit for damage initiation. Thus, the influence of the presence of optical fiber sensors in beams of this magnitude has been shown to be insignificant.

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